

Behavioral self-regulation development in at-risk families: the role of family resources

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ABSTRACT

Children from disadvantaged families are at greater risk of developing regulation difficulties. Research suggests that family-level resources such as parental education or income are related to self-regulation development. However, most studies looking at the role of family resources have used single estimators of socioeconomic status or applied a composite score, neglecting that an interplay of resources may affect self-regulation outcomes. In $N = 248$ at-risk children (M_{age} : 65.7 months, 51% female), we examined the effect of economic, cultural, and social family resources on behavioral self-regulation in kindergarten. Results showed that family income, maternal education, and available help in child-rearing predicted the Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders task performance. The results indicate that behavioral self-regulation is associated with different family resources beyond socioeconomic status.

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Children from disadvantaged families are at greater risk for developing behavioral regulation difficulties (e.g. Lengua et al., 2015; Miech, Essex, & Goldsmith, 2001; Ponitz et al., 2008). Research in at-risk families indicates that family resources such as parental education, income, and native nationality status is positively related to self-regulation development (Köckeritz, Klinkhammer, & Salisch, 2010; Sektnan, McClelland, Acock, & Morrison, 2010; Wanless, McClelland, Tominey, & Acock, 2011). Most studies examining the role of family resources apply either a socio-economic composite score or single indicators of socioeconomic status (SES; e.g. income or level of education). Thus, the specific contribution of each resource type for self-regulation development remains unclear. Within European samples, longitudinal studies on psychosocially vulnerable families are scarce. We aim to address these gaps by examining the relationship between economic, cultural, and social family resources on kindergarten children's behavioral self-regulation (B-SR) skills in at-risk families in Switzerland.

The development of behavioral self-regulation in context

Behavioral self-regulation (skills) is the ability to regulate one's behavior to meet situational demands. A frequently used measure to assess B-SR is the HTKS (Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders)

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task (McClelland & Cameron, 2012; Ponitza, McClelland, Matthews, & Morrison, 2009). This set of skills is central to school readiness and later academic success (Edossa, Schroeders, Weinert, & Artelt, 2018; Ursache, Blair, & Raver, 2012; Wanless, McClelland, Acock, et al., 2011). B-SR develops rapidly between the ages of three to seven and involves higher-order cognitive processes, such as executive functions (EF: working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility; Montroy, Bowles, Skibbe, McClelland, & Morrison, 2016; Wanless et al., 2011). Evidence from cross-sectional, longitudinal, and neuroimaging research shows tremendous development in behavioral regulation and executive functions between the ages of three to seven (Davidson, Amso, Anderson, & Diamond, 2006; Montroy et al., 2016; Zelazo et al., 2003). Fundamental brain maturation processes, e.g. rapid synaptic growth and pruning, occur in relation to experience, and the interconnectedness between regulatory domains, such as cognition, emotion, and behavior underlines the importance of this period (Carlson & Wang, 2007; Diamond, 2013). Early regulation abilities have been shown to predict academic and health outcomes over a long developmental span into adolescence and adulthood (Edossa et al., 2018; Evans & Rosenbaum, 2008; Moffitt et al., 2011). Thus, early childhood marks a particularly critical phase in self-regulation development, making it even more pressing to understand it in full detail.

Developmental system theories propose that interindividual differences in developmental trajectories result from a complex interconnection between child and environmental factors (e.g. Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2007; Overton, 2013). The concept of experiential canalization (Blair & Raver, 2012), for example, emphasizes the impact of (long-term) contextual factors on the development of self-regulation processes. Empirical evidence suggested that contextual and social processes significantly shape B-SR (Karreman, van Tuijl, van Aken, & Deković, 2006). Compared to the body of research on intraindividual development and parenting shaping self-regulation development, contextual factors have received a little less attention. However, one contextual factor that has been studied extensively is SES. In the literature, SES has been applied as an overarching umbrella term with various operationalizations. Some studies apply a composite score, combining different aspects of the socioeconomic status (e.g. Galindo & Fuller, 2010), while other studies focus on single, separate constructs (e.g. income, parental education). In either approach, the unique contributions of single types of family resources remain unclear (Köckeritz et al., 2010; Raver, Blair, & Willoughby, 2013). By analyzing the single constructs unique effects in a comprehensive analysis, we aim to contribute to a more fine-grained understanding of how each resource uniquely affects B-SR.

Family resources and the development of behavioral self-regulation

Few studies have systematically addressed the effect of family resources on B-SR development. Family resources are defined as factors that play a supportive role for families in dealing with stressors and affect parental adjustment, parental behavior, and child outcome positively (Dunst, 2021; Van Horn, Bellis, & Snyder, 2001). Bronfenbrenner's bioecological model of human development (Bronfenbrenner, 1989; Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2007) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the impact of these resources. The model includes interrelated systems contributing uniquely to the development process. While the microsystem includes the most proximate factors related to the child (i.e. parents, siblings, peers, and school), the exo- and macro contexts are more distant but still influential for child development. Within the microsystem, key resources are family income, parental education, and parental language skills. These resources shape proximal processes as fundamental mechanisms through which development occurs. The exosystem includes broader social structures that indirectly affect the child, such as parents' workplaces and community services, highlighting available services and networks as a resource that may impact child development. At the macrosystem level, societal norms, cultural values, and policies shape the resources available to families.

Using a different terminology but also referring to resources available to the family, Bourdieu (1986) differentiated three forms of family capital, i.e. economic, cultural, and social capital. These

forms of capital shape not only family well-being but also an individual's life trajectories, social status, and cultural participation (Bourdieu, 1986). Building upon Bourdieu's theoretical framework on family capital, family resources can go beyond a family's socioeconomic assets (e.g. income, education) and include social resources and language competencies that may have a positive impact on child development (Osher, Cantor, Berg, Steyer, & Rose, 2020; Palacios & Bohlmann, 2020; Van Horn et al., 2001). Both Bronfenbrenner's and Bourdieu's frameworks recognize the importance of various levels of influence on child development and underscore the importance of economic, cultural, and social family resources in shaping developmental outcomes. Despite these influential theoretical contributions, little is known about how different resources, i.e. economic, cultural, and social resources, within at-risk families affects B-SR development over time. To date, longitudinal effects of different family resources beyond economic resources on self-regulation development have rarely been systematically investigated in urban at-risk families.

Economic resources – household income

Higher family income has been linked to better B-SR skills in mixed- and low-income samples in different tasks such as delay of gratification, HTKS, and EF tasks in school-aged and kindergarten children (Lengua et al., 2015; Raver et al., 2013; Wanless, McClelland, Tominey, et al., 2011). Lengua et al. (2015), for example, found a positive relationship between B-SR skills (effortful control) and income in a kindergarten sample. While the role of income and other economic factors on self-regulation is well established, the impact of income is less clear if other resources are considered too.

Cultural resources – level of education and proficiency in the local language

Cultural resources are defined as symbolic resources supporting social upward mobility within stratified societies, including education and linguistic skills (Lareau & Weininger, 2005). Maternal education as a protective factor for positive child development in adverse contexts is well established (Walker et al., 2011). A large body of research shows that maternal education level is positively related to children's self-regulation skills (Miech et al., 2001; Sektan et al., 2010; Wanless, McClelland, Acock, et al., 2011). Studies rarely assessed maternal education, including both income measures and social resources. Again, this constraint makes it impossible to disentangle the specific effects of different types of resources at play.

The ability to speak the local language facilitates a range of interactions in everyday life for immigrant parents. To the best of our knowledge, no study within Europe has examined the effect of maternal language proficiency in the local language on children's B-SR development. Other migration-related family characteristics have been linked to B-SR. Children with at least one immigrant parent showed lower B-SR skills and emotional understanding compared to children with native parents (Köckeritz et al., 2010). Palacios and Bohlmann (2020) found negative associations between executive functions and speaking a non-native primary home language in Latino children at age five. The mechanisms underlying the reported disadvantages remain unclear. At the same time, other family resources such as social resources, were not accounted for.

Social resources – social activities and available help in child-rearing

Social resources are defined as resources in the form of social relationships. Social resources encompass subjective measures, such as perceived social support, and objective measures, such as the overall sum of social activities or the size of the social network (e.g. Gottlieb & Bergen, 2010). Social resources mitigate consequences of inadequate parenting for children through, e.g. providing assistance in child-care tasks, or establishing common child-rearing standards, and can reduce the risk of child maltreatment (Gracia & Musitu, 2003). Social support can have an impact on both the caregiver and the child; social activities provide cognitive stimulation and provide input for socioemotional learning (Collins, Madsen, & Susman-Stillman, 2005). In the self-regulation literature, social resources have received less attention than economic or

cultural resources. In the current study two social resources will be included: social activities and available help in child-rearing.

Social activities are conceptualized as activities within a personal social network (e.g. informal meetings with friends with/without same-aged children; Cochran & Niego, 2002). Social activities convey characteristics of the personal social network, such as the size and composition of the network, and the frequency and nature of the contact with the personal social network of intra- and extra-family members (Wrzus, Hänel, Wagner, & Neyer, 2013). Social activities were recognized as protective factors on the parental level, supporting well-being, or providing support in the face of hardship (Balaji et al., 2007). Research on direct effects of social activities on B-SR is very limited. However, indirect effects through parental factors suggest that social activities might play a role in children's B-SR. For example, extended and supportive social networks were associated with lower levels of negative parenting (harsh, controlling, or intrusive parenting), which heightens risks for B-SR difficulties (Hashima & Amato, 1994; Jennings, Stagg, & Connors, 1991; Ringoot et al., 2022; Valcan, Davis, & Pino-Pasternak, 2018).

Empirical findings relating available help in child-rearing to B-SR development are limited. Based on the literature, we assume that the available help in child-rearing might affect child B-SR through parental-level effects. More specifically, tangible social support was found to enhance nurturing parenting behavior and lower harsh parenting and parental stress. These parental competencies were, in turn, positively linked to behavioral and cognitive self-regulation abilities in toddlers and school-aged children (Ceballo & McLoyd, 2002; Planalp, Nowak, Tran, Lefever, & Braungart-Rieker, 2022; Valcan et al., 2018).

In summary, previous evidence indicates direct or indirect effects of economic, cultural, and social resources within the family on B-SR in preschool children. However, these findings stem predominately from studies including one or maximally two resource types, leaving the unique contributions of each type within a set of family resources on B-SR development undefined. Further, the importance of specific family resources in at-risk families could vary depending on the macro-context.

Family resources in context

Despite the fact that every fourth child experiences some form of adversity in Europe (e.g. poverty; Eurostat, 2023), most research on adversity is conducted in the USA. Because risks and effective interventions may vary with the welfare system in place, having European data is indispensable to understanding cascading adversity dynamics for child development. Family resources are embedded within the larger macro context. Macro-level factors, such as the social welfare system and the early childhood education and care systems (ECEC) may vary locally (Jungmann, Dähne, Sierau, Serbati, & Dugravier, 2017). Different studies with non-at-risk samples in different macro contexts, i.e. US, Norway, Korea, Taiwan found for example mixed results for the association between maternal education and B-SR (Lenes, Gonzales, Størksen, & McClelland, 2020; Son, Lee, & Sung, 2013; Wanless et al., 2016). These cross-country differences can be attributed to two different factors: (a) differences in caregiver regulatory behavior and parental practices, and (b) differences in the macro-level context (Lenes et al., 2020). In comparison with other European countries, Switzerland is a high-income country with a relatively low poverty rate and well-developed childcare around birth. Despite these financial and social resources, there is still a shortfall in supply for socially vulnerable families, and approximately 30% of families are not reached through communal early childhood support (Jungmann et al., 2017). Social connectedness outside the family was found to vary significantly between European countries, arguably due to differences in welfare systems (Surkalim et al., 2022; Yoon, Maguire-Jack, Ploss, Benavidez, & Chang, 2023). How this complex interconnection between different resources and macro-level factors is related to B-SR in at-risk children is unclear. The present study aims to refine our understanding of how family resources affect B-SR development in at-risk children within the context of a high-income country.

The present study

The current study examines the longitudinal associations between different family resources in early childhood, i.e. economic, cultural, and social resources, and B-SR in kindergarten children from at-risk families. To examine these associations, data from an intervention study in a high-income European country aiming to foster educational opportunities for children in at-risk families were used. Stepwise regression analyses are computed to examine the different resources in one comprehensive analysis. Through such an approach, we aim to gain insights into the unique contribution of each resource on B-SR in early childhood. Overall, we expect a positive relationship between family resources and children's B-SR. More specifically, we expect higher self-regulatory skills in kindergarten children whose families reported higher economic, cultural, and social resources in early childhood.

Methods

To address the research question, we used data from the ZEPPELIN project, a longitudinal intervention study aiming to enhance developmental opportunities for children exposed to accumulated psychosocial stressors (Lanfranchi & Neuhauser, 2013). Families with multiple psychosocial risk factors were recruited around childbirth through medical, mental health, and social services in an urban area of Switzerland. Data from ages 0 (T0), 1 (T1), 3 (T3), and 5 (T5; kindergarten) were used for the current analysis. For T0, T1, and T3, data were collected through trained interviewers in the family's homes. For T5, the child outcome measure was assessed in kindergarten. The Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich approved the ZEPPELIN study protocol (Approval Nb. KEK-ZH 2013-0278).

Sample

The final sample included 248 children from families with multiple psychosocial risk factors from the German-speaking part of Switzerland. Sample characteristics are presented in Table 1. Families were selected based on psychosocial risk levels around childbirth. The psychosocial risk screening was conducted in multiple steps, first by a multi-professional network (parent-counselling, health-, and social services) in ambulatory settings, and finally by certified parent educators in a home visit. Seventy-four percent of all screened families indicated a psychosocial stress level exceeding 40 points on the Heidelberg Stress Scale (Sidor, Eickhorst, Stasch, & Cierpka, 2012). A score beyond 40 points indicates psychosocial stress on multiple dimensions, i.e. child-related- (e.g. early regulatory problems), familial- (e.g. conflicts) and personal- (e.g. low education), social- (e.g. social isolation), and material-related stress (e.g. finances). The authors of the scale define the cut-off value of ≥ 40 points on the overall psychosocial stress scale to indicate a need for support. Families with no permanent residency permit, children with severe illness or disability, or parents requiring long-term

Table 1. Descriptives of the sample.

	<i>M (SD) or %</i>
Mother age, at birth of focal child	29.61 (5.69)
Mother with no or only compulsory education (%)	39.91
Mother with foreign nationality (%)	72.80
Single-motherhood (age 1) (%)	11.69
Heidelberger Stress scale (age 1)	46.32 (16.17)
Mother social welfare (age 3) (%)	15.73
Child born preterm (%)	13.79
Child female sex (%)	52.42
Twins ^a (age 1) (%)	9.96
Number of siblings (age 3)	.96 (.85)

Note: $N = 248$.

^aTwin siblings were randomly excluded to include only one child per family.

psychiatric care or other treatments, or those involved in child protection procedures, were excluded from the study. For further information on the sampling procedure and high-risk sample inclusion criteria, see Neuhauser et al. (2015). The interviews were conducted at home with the mothers (97% at age one, 99% at age three). Mothers from 57 different nationalities were represented in the sample. The most frequent nationalities were 12% Turkish, 12% Kosovo, 12% Portugal. All children were born between June 2011 and September 2012. Individual testing (i.e. outcome measure) took place when children were attending the first year of kindergarten.

Measures

Family resources

Descriptive statistics for all variables are presented in Table 2. The data on the family resources were extracted from parental interviews at ages one and three. The scales were designed for the ZEPPELIN study. If necessary, a professional translator assisted during the interviews. All resources served as predictor variables.

Economic resources – household income (T3). In an open-question format, parents indicated their family income. The monthly net income included working income and social support services (e.g. unemployment benefits and disability pensions).

Cultural resources – maternal education (T1). Based on the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED-2011; UNESCO, 2012), maternal education ranged from none to tertiary education (1 = no compulsory school, 2 = only compulsory school, 3 = upper secondary education, 4 = tertiary education).

Cultural resources – maternal German proficiency (T3). After the home visit, the interviewer rated the maternal language proficiency on a four-level Likert scale. The scale ranges from 1 = no German proficiency to 4 = communication in German is trouble-free.

Social resources – social activities (T3). Social activities included measures of the frequency of contact with friends of the caregiver (ranging from 1 = none to 5 = several times a week), the count of friends (ranging from 1 = no one to 4 = 5 or more people), and child's contacts with other children outside of the family home (ranging from 1 = never to 5 = usually daily). All three types of social activities included only outside-of-family contacts and contacts with both the same and different main spoken languages. The total sum describes the total of social activities. Due to scaling differences within the subscales, only z-standardized values were provided in Table 2.

Social resources – available help in child-rearing (T3). Available help in child-rearing was assessed with twelve items for two child-rearing needs: babysitting ('Can [parents/friends/...] babysit your baby for you if needed?') and receiving advice ('Can you get advice on child-rearing topics from

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for all variables.

Variables	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	min	max	Skewness	Kurtosis
HTKS (kindergarten)	26.67	15.38	0	55.59	-.1	-.72
Early regulatory problems (ERP)	.31	.47	0	1	.79	-1.37
Household income (in Swiss francs)	5637.24	2282.13	1647	12921	.6	.52
Maternal education	2.64	.89	1	4	-.26	-.67
Maternal German proficiency	3.18	.91	1	4	-.85	-.32
Social activities ^a	0	1	-2.97	1.88	-.61	.44
Available help in child-rearing	2.19	1.24	0	8	.75	.93

Note: *N* = 248.

^aFor social activities, only z-standardized values are available due to measurement scale differences in the underlying subscales.

[parents/friends/ ...]?). The dichotomous items indicated the perceived availability of (noncommercial) helpers in six categories (parents, siblings, other relatives, friends, colleagues/acquaintances, and neighbors). A sum score was computed based on the 'yes' answers and ranges from zero to a possible maximum of 12.

Outcome variable

Behavioral self-regulation (T5). B-SR was measured with the Head-Toes-Knees-Shoulders task (Ponitz et al., 2009). In this task, children were asked to do the opposite of what they were told based on four different verbal cues to touch either the head, shoulders, knees, or toes (e.g. 'If I say touch your toes, touch your head,' 'If I say touch your shoulders, touch your knees'). The task consists of 30 items. Correct execution was coded with two points, self-corrected responses with one point, and incorrect responses with zero points (maximum of 60 points). Children were tested in kindergarten by trained research assistants during individual sessions at the end of the first kindergarten year (mean age = 65.7 months, SD = 3.7 months). Ten percent of the children received zero points for their execution of the task and one child reached the maximum score. All were included in the analysis. Similar to other studies (McClelland et al., 2014; Montroy et al., 2016), the Cronbach's alpha for the HTKS was high, $\alpha = .96$.

Control variables

Early childhood regulatory problems. To prevent biases by dispositional child factors, early regulatory problems were controlled for. Early regulatory problems are defined as dispositional, early occurring regulatory dysfunction in infants (Papousek, Schieche, & Wurmser, 2007). Early regulatory problems within the first six months after birth were assessed through a single-item question on persisting regulatory difficulties in, e.g. feeding, sleeping, or crying (1 = yes, 0 = no) as part of a risk screening questionnaire assessing family risk factors including personal-, familial, social-, material-, and child related risks (Neuhauser et al., 2015). The question was rated by professionals in an ambulatory screening process during recruitment and thoroughly confirmed by certified parent educator during the home visit.

Intervention groups. The data used in this study stem from the longitudinal ZEPPELIN project which aims to enhance developmental opportunities for at-risk children in Switzerland. The project focusses on the early detection of developmental delays or health issues, fostering positive parent-child-interactions, and strong child development in vulnerable families, based on the curriculum of the US-home visiting program *Parents as Teachers* (PAT; PATNC, 2011). In the first three years, families assigned to the intervention group received at least ten home visits yearly by a professional and attended a monthly group meeting. Participants in the control group did not participate in the home-visiting program and group meeting but had access to the regular municipality community services. T-tests showed no group differences on any variables in this study (see 'statistical analysis'- section). The assignment to the intervention groups was used as a control variable in the analyses (1 = intervention group, 0 = control group).

Statistical analysis

All analyses were performed with R (R Core Team, 2013). To deal with missing data, multiple imputations were performed based on the iterative PCA method, using the R package missMDA (Josse & Husson, 2016) and FactoMineR (Lê, Josse, & Husson, 2008). To test for the assumption of missing completely at random (MCAR) prior to the imputation, the Little's test for MCAR was conducted, yielding insignificant likeliness of a violation of the MCAR assumption, $\chi^2(1336, N = 248) = 1348, p = .4$ (Little, 1988). Fifty-six percent of the sample had at least one missing data point. Seventy-seven percent of all data points were present. To ensure the accuracy of the imputations, diagnostic measures and a leave-one-out cross-validation technique were employed. First, the imputed data

and the observed data were compared in terms of means, standard deviation, and distribution. Subsequently, the leave-one-out cross-validation technique was conducted by temporarily deleting observed data points and imputing the missing values based on the remaining data (e.g. Wong, 2015). The imputed data and the deleted data were then checked through Pearson's correlations with regard to their similarity. The diagnostic check and the leave-one-out validation technique confirmed the accuracy of the imputations. Further, the stepwise regression analyses conducted using the Full-Information-Maximum-Likelihood method in R resulted in similar effect sizes as for the multiple imputation data. Data points that deviated more than three SD from the mean were capped and replaced with the value of the 1st resp. 99th percentile. All variables were standardized to z-values.

Before pooling the data of the two groups, potential group differences were tested with two-sided t-tests. No group differences were found for any variable in this study (B-SR, $t(259) = -1.1$, $p = .29$; income, $t(259) = 1.3$, $p = .20$; maternal education, $t(259) = -.4$, $p = .67$; maternal language proficiency, $t(259) = -1.1$, $p = .29$; social activity, $t(259) = .2$, $p = .84$; available help in child-rearing, $t(259) = 1.0$, $p = .32$; early regulatory problems, $t(259) = -.6$, $p = .54$). As there were no group differences on any of the variables used in this study, data of the two groups was collapsed.

A stepwise regression analysis examined how the different resources (i.e. predictor variables) were related to behavioral self-regulation. Three types of resources were added consecutively based on the empirical relevance of each resource type to the model (z-standardized scores): economic, cultural, and social resources.

Results

The correlation matrix showed non-substantial to small correlations between the predictor variables (see Table 3). The correlation coefficients indicate that although family resources were interrelated, each measure still accounted for separate constructs. The highest correlation was found between maternal education and income ($r = .31$).

The results of the stepwise regression analysis of family resources (economic, cultural, and social) as predictors of HTKS in kindergarten are presented in Table 4. Step one of the stepwise regression analysis contained only early regulatory problems and treatment groups as control variables. Step two included the control variables and economic resources. In the second step, family income at age three significantly predicted the performance in the HTKS task in kindergarten ($\beta = .28$). In step three, cultural resources were added to the model in step two. In this step, income ($\beta = .19$), maternal education ($\beta = .17$), and maternal language proficiency in German ($\beta = .14$) at age three all predicted the performance in the HTKS task in kindergarten. In the final model (step four), social resources were added to the model in step three. In the final model, income ($\beta = .18$), maternal education ($\beta = .18$), and available help in child-rearing ($\beta = .14$) at age three all predicted individual

Table 3. Correlation matrix between all predictor variables and HTKS in kindergarten.

Variables	HTKS	ERP	Treatment group	Income	Education	German	Social activities	Available help in child-rearing
HTKS (kindergarten)	–							
Early regulatory problems	.09	–						
Treatment group	.06	.01	–					
Household income	.27***	.11 [†]	-.07	–				
Maternal education	.27***	.12 [†]	.02	.31***	–			
Maternal German proficiency	.23***	.09	.05	.21***	.24***	–		
Social activities	-.01	-.06	-.01	.07	-.03	.02	–	
Available help in child-rearing	.20***	.07	-.07	.19***	.09	.27***	.05	–

Note: $N = 248$; $^{\dagger} p < .1$; *** $p < .001$; EPR: early regulatory problems.

Table 4. Results of hierarchical regression analysis predicting HTKS in kindergarten.

Variables	β	[95% CI]	Overall model <i>F</i> , (<i>df</i>)	(adj.) R^2	ΔR^2
Step 1			1.33 (2, 245)	.003	
Early regulatory problems	.19	[−.08, .45]			
Treatment group	.11	[−.14, .36]			
Step 2			7.49 (3, 244)***	.08	.08***
Early regulatory problems	.12	[−.14, .37]			
Treatment group	.15	[−.06, .41]			
Household income	.27***	[.17, .41]			
Step 3			7.77 (5, 242)***	.12	.05***
Early regulatory problems	.06	[−.19, .31]			
Treatment group	.12	[−.09, .37]			
Household income	.19***	[.09, .34]			
Maternal education	.17**	[.05, .30]			
Maternal German proficiency	.14*	[.01, .24]			
Step 4			6.24 (7, 240)***	.13	<.01
Early regulatory problems	.06	[−.20, .30]			
Treatment group	.14	[−.07, .38]			
Household income	.18**	[.07, .32]			
Maternal education	.18**	[.06, .30]			
Maternal German proficiency	.11 [†]	[−.03, .22]			
Social activities	−.02	[−.14, .09]			
Available help in child-rearing	.13*	[.00, .24]			

Note: $N = 248$; [†] $p < .1$; * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

differences in the HTKS task in kindergarten. Maternal German proficiency no longer predicted the HTKS performance after including social resources. Economic and cultural resources explained a substantial amount of variance in the outcome measure. Including social resources with economic and cultural resources did not contribute to an overall better model. Early regulatory problems and treatment group did not predict HTKS performance in any of the models. The final model explained 13% of the variance in B-SR.

Discussion

The present study investigated the longitudinal effect of family resources in early childhood on behavioral self-regulation (B-SR) in at-risk children. In a stepwise regression analysis, we examined the associations between three resource types, i.e. economic (household income), cultural (maternal education and language proficiency), social resources (social activities and available help in child-rearing), and children's B-SR skills. The results indicated a positive link between resources within each class of family resources and children's B-SR in kindergarten. While controlling for early regulation problems after birth, different family resources accounted for a substantial amount of inter-individual variance in B-SR in kindergarten. In the final model, household income, maternal education, and available help in child-rearing positively predicted child B-SR. Including social resources did not explain a significant additional portion of the outcome variance; however, available help in child-rearing was a significant predictor, suggesting a shared variance between social resources and the first two empirically more prominent socioeconomic predictors.

Income, education, and available help in child-rearing foster behavioral self-regulation in at-risk families

In line with previous research, we found a positive effect of income and maternal education on B-SR in kindergarten. Similar to previous studies with at-risk and non-at-risk US samples (Lengua et al., 2015; Miech et al., 2001; Sektan et al., 2010), early childhood family income predicted B-SR. The positive effect of maternal education on B-SR is in line with previous research in at-risk samples (Blair &

Raver, 2012; Hughes & Ensor, 2009). However, a study comparing the association between maternal education and B-SR in non-at-risk samples in the US and in Norway found no association in Norway (Lenes et al., 2020). The authors speculated that differences in the social welfare system and ECEC between the US and Norway could have contributed to the results. Although Switzerland has a high-quality welfare system, our results show that low maternal education remains predictive for lower B-SR within this at-risk sample. Thus, it may be that the association between maternal education and B-SR not only varies as a function of the welfare system in place but also differs for risk vs. non-risk families. More research, including broader family resources while considering macro-level factors in at-risk samples, is needed to refine our understanding of the importance of family resources in relation to macro-level factors.

A novel finding is that mothers' reports on more available help in child-rearing was positively related to children's B-SR. This indicates that in addition to measures of SES, better B-SR in kindergarten is also related to social resources in the form of available help in early childhood in at-risk families. The correlational results provided a hint that socioeconomic markers might be differentially associated with available help, because especially mothers with low household income seem to report less available help. No similar association was found for level of education and available help. In addition, available help is positively linked to German language proficiency. Taken together, this pattern could suggest that available help and asking for help might be facilitated through German language proficiency and higher household income rather than through the level of education. However, this is speculative, and further research is needed to examine these relations longitudinally.

Other than expected, no association between social activities and B-SR were found. Two aspects could be considered more thoroughly in future studies: First, a more differentiated classification of social activities (e.g. setting, characteristics of participants, interaction quality), and second, an examination of intra-family social activities. Social activities might come at a cost, e.g. time. It is possible that these costs are higher for low-SES mothers compared to more privileged mothers (for a review, see Taylor, 2011), thus limiting the effect of the resource.

A broad conceptualization of family resources on behavioral self-regulation development

The comprehensive analysis suggests that multiple resources within the family have the potential to promote B-SR in kindergarten. Focusing solely on individual facets of family assets could result in overlooking valuable resources for child development with significant implications for both research and intervention purposes. The effect of income and education on B-SR was replicated in this study within an at-risk sample in a high-income country. Income and education may provide children with better opportunities to learn and develop skills to follow and integrate complex instructions and to overact dominant responses (Valcan et al., 2018). While a foreign at-home language can be an influential predictor of children's B-SR skills in kindergarten (Palacios & Bohlmann, 2020), in this sample, the effect of maternal local language proficiency is less strong compared to other resources (i.e. available help, income, and education). It is important to note that economic, cultural, and social resources vary over time and interventions could focus on to fostering more malleable resources, such as available help.

Contextualizing the present results more precisely, Switzerland is classified as a high-income country with a strong welfare system. Despite many available services, the share of parents' private contribution to ECEC is high compared to other OECD countries (Faeh & Vogt, 2021). For families with low-economical resources, these services are even more difficult to access, and the families' social resources may be more existential than for more privileged families. Thus, future research on B-SR development may consider to include social resources too to disentangle promoting factors for B-SR inside and outside of the family. On policy level, the results indicate that early childhood support programs that focus on enhancing financial stability and accessible education and training for mothers in at-risk families might positively affect the B-SR development. In addition to subsidized daycare, establishing a child-rearing network, especially for mothers with low German

skills, might contribute to a positive B-SR development during the preschool years. The results indicate that the effects of family resources in early childhood persist into the kindergarten years. Comprehensive studies are necessary to fully understand how these resources influence B-SR development leading up to kindergarten and the best timing of interventions. Sustained interventions into the kindergarten year might further ensure positive outcomes on the B-SR development. In addition to a broader conceptualization of family resources, a more dynamic perspective and the inclusion of subjective perceptions of resources will deepen our understanding of the interconnection between different family resources in self-regulation development. Building upon the variable-centered approach, future work with family-centered (also known as 'person-centered') approaches that explore common patterns of resources shared between families while also considering malleable family resources may also be beneficial for gaining a better understanding of the importance of resources within individual family constellations across diverse ecological contexts.

Limitations

Several constraints limit the current findings. Stability and changes in the resources between birth and age three on B-SR are unaccounted for. Several single-item measures were used, e.g. for income, education, maternal language skills, and early regulatory problems. While multi-item assessments would ensure higher validity and reliability of the measures, in reality, assessing variables through multiple items is time-consuming and demanding for the participants. The findings on social activities apply to extra-family contacts only as we excluded intra-family social activities due to a highly skewed distribution (high frequency of daily family contacts). However, studies on family support have shown the significance of family ties in satisfying social support- and closeness needs in highly prevalent in at-risk families (e.g. Campos, Ullman, Aguilera, & Dunkel Schetter, 2014). Thus, further research should include both extra- and intra-family social activities to gain a more comprehensive picture of social activities and self-regulation development. Lastly, only one B-SR measurement was included, limiting the generalizability of the current findings. Using additional B-SR measurements, including measurements with high ecological validity (e.g. teacher-reported BRIEF-P; Gioia, Andrus, & Isquith, 1996; McCoy, 2019) and measures that capture regulatory skills that have high real-life relevance to children in their specific family context (e.g. Alcalá, Rogoff, Mejía-Arauz, Coppens, & Dexter, 2014) would be needed to advance our understanding of B-SR in the context of adversity.

Conclusions

Children's ability to regulate their behavior to meet social and situational demands are related to available resources within a family. The results showed that family income, maternal education, and available help in child-rearing in early childhood predicted B-SR in kindergarten children in at-risk families in Switzerland. Intercorrelations between family resources indicated a complex pattern that does not support an 'all-or-nothing' notion of the availability of family resources but instead differentiated associations between types of resources. These findings add to the literature on B-SR development of at-risk children growing up in a high-income country. Further research is required to achieve a more precise understanding of how different family resources promote B-SR in at-risk families across different macro-contexts.

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Appendix

Table A1. Descriptive statistics for all variables prior to imputation.

Variables	n	M	Non-standardized		
			SD	min	max
HTKS (Kindergarten)	160	27.77	18.26	0	60
Early regulatory problems (ERP)	248	.31	.47	0	1
Household income (in Swiss francs)	190	5663.57	2664.87	1000	15000
Maternal education	247	2.64	.89	1	4
Maternal German proficiency	206	3.19	.98	1	4
Social activities ^a	201	−.2	2.07	−.53	4.1
Available help in child-rearing	159	2.23	1.49	0	8

^aFor social activities, only z-standardized values are available due to measurement scale differences in the underlying subscales.